

Children's Story Book on Science and Social Learning Oriented Pancasila Student Profile

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ABSTRAK

Ciri utama pelajar pancasila belum sepenuhnya dipahami apa dan bagaimana oleh peserta didik. Sehingga dalam penanaman nilai-nilai profil pelajar pancasila memerlukan cara yang tepat. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menciptakan buku cerita anak yang berorientasi profil pelajar Pancasila untuk siswa kelas IV. Jenis penelitian ini adalah penelitian pengembangan menggunakan model penelitian 4-D. Subyek dalam penelitian ini adalah tiga orang ahli, guru, dan siswa kelas 4 SD yang berjumlah 34 orang. Metode pengumpulan data dengan wawancara dan kuesioner. Teknik analisis data menggunakan analisis kualitatif dan kuantitatif. Hasil perhitungan kriteria uji kepraktisan respon siswa terhadap buku cerita diperoleh hasil 98,5 memenuhi kriteria sangat praktis. Berdasarkan hasil perhitungan rata-rata gain skor, diperoleh hasil rata-rata 0,71, artinya buku cerita yang dikembangkan memiliki tingkat efektifitas tinggi. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa buku cerita yang dikembangkan memiliki tingkat efektifitas tinggi dan dapat digunakan dalam proses pembelajaran. Implikasi penelitian ini dapat dijadikan bahan ajar untuk mencontohkan dan membudayakan nilai-nilai profil pelajar Pancasila.

ABSTRACT

The main characteristics of Pancasila students are not yet fully understood by students. So teaching the values of the Pancasila student profile requires the right way. This study aims to produce a children's storybook oriented to the profile of Pancasila students for fourth-grade students. This type of research is development research and uses a 4-D research model. The subjects in this study were three experts, teachers, and 34 grade 4. Based on the calculation of the practicality test criteria for student responses to story books, the results were 98.5. These results indicate that the storybook meets the very practical criteria. Based on the calculation of the average gain score, the average result is 0.71, meaning that the storybook developed has a high level of effectiveness. The result of the development of this research is a children's storybook oriented to the profile of Pancasila students for chapter 6, Indonesiaku Kaya Budaya Class IV SD/MI, which was developed based on the 4D development model. So, it can be concluded that the storybook developed has a high level of effectiveness and can be used in the learning process. The implications of this research can be used as teaching materials to exemplify and cultivate the values of the Pancasila student profile.

1. INTRODUCTION

Pancasila is a solid ideology in Indonesia, so Pancasila guides any activity in people's lives, especially when dealing with people of different ethnicities, races, and religions (Dewantara & Nurgiansah, 2021; Nurgiansyah, 2021). Life in the millennial era demands the implementation of Pancasila values to adapt to the reality of change, especially the dynamics of the lives of the younger generation of Indonesian students (Anggraini et al., 2020; Asmaroini, 2016). The Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Education and Culture for 2020-2024 is contained in the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 22 of 2020, which mandates the vision and mission of education in Indonesia through the Pancasila student profile. A profile and future expectations about student character figures desired by the Indonesian people through government policies. With Indonesian cultural identity and Pancasila values rooted in Indonesian society in the future, it will become an open society with global citizenship, able to accept and utilize the diversity of sources, experiences,

and values from various cultures in the world, but at the same time does not lose its characteristics and identity. Characteristically. Through the Pancasila student profile, Indonesian education wants to make students in all corners of the country understand better, appreciate, and implement the values of Pancasila (Basri et al., 2021; Ismail et al., 2021).

The implementation of activities oriented toward the main characteristics of the class-based Pancasila student profile is carried out with project-based activities, both those that are integrated with subjects and those that are not integrated with subjects (Ardhyantama, 2017; Rachmawati et al., 2022). The project-based activities carried out seem more separate in each subject. It has an impact on the density of project assignments carried out by students (I. M. A Dharma, 2019; Krismawati, 2019). So that students have not fully understand the main characteristics of Pancasila students. So teaching the values of the Pancasila student profile requires the right way. Based on the interview results, the teacher also conveyed that of the six main characteristics of the Pancasila student profile instilled in students, the most entrenched values of students were religiosity and cooperation. Meanwhile, independent values, critical reasoning, and creative and global insight are still not maximally entrenched. Variations in parenting patterns and environmental stimuli cause the lack of a culture of the value of independence, critical reasoning, and creative and global insight. On the other hand, the value of independence, critical reasoning, and creative and global insight does not appear and can be done by children. Habituation and role models are needed for children to learn and apply them as early as possible. This is inseparable from the role of parents at home as a place for children to learn for the first time before there is a stimulus from the surrounding environment. Educators will help children learn and maximize the basic values of each family. These differences in parenting patterns create new challenges for educators. Teachers also expect media or facilities that teachers can use to model the profile of Pancasila students, especially in fourth grade, which requires an image that can be imitated and cultivated. This problem, if left unchecked, will have a negative impact.

One solution that can be done is to use learning media in learning activities. One of the media that can be chosen is children's story books. Story books, especially picture story books, are easy-to-use media because they do not require other additional tools or special facilities, so it can be said that their use is very practical (S. P Apriliani & Radia, 2020; Sapri et al., 2022). Reading picture story books allows early childhood to learn various things in different contexts and atmospheres (Siwi Pawestri Apriliani & Radia, 2020; Faroh & Setiawan, 2018; Hayati & Suparno, 2020). The positive things picture story books offer for students can be interpreted and implemented in their daily lives. Images have benefits; among others, they can attract attention, are unique, abstract things can be clarified, and can illustrate a process (Sun et al., 2022; Takacs & Bus, 2018). Characteristics of picture story books for children are books with pictures and text that tell a story together, with a theme appropriate for children (I Made Aditya Dharma, 2019; Purwani, 2020). Of course, this opinion is very much in line with efforts to implement a class-based Pancasila student profile. There are so many benefits of children's story books, namely as an introductory medium in learning and also as a means of modeling and teaching the main characteristics of Pancasila student profiles, so it is very good if children's story books are used in learning in elementary schools, especially in the fourth grade of elementary school.

Several previous research findings stated that story books were effectively used as a companion book for the 2013 curriculum books used in the learning process in fifth grade, especially the Environmental Friendship theme because students experienced changes for the better in their attitudes and learning outcomes (Aditya Dharma, 2019). In addition, the resulting storybook is effectively used as a companion book for the 2013 Curriculum book, which is used in the learning process in the first grade of elementary school, especially the theme of My Passion, because students experience changes for the better in their attitudes and literacy (Pratiwi, 2017). Picture storybooks positively impact early childhood understanding, especially regarding examples of actions following the values of *servite et amate* (Halim & Munthe, 2019a). The influence of picture story books on children's knowledge of disaster management (Solfiah et al., 2020). The difference between this study and previous studies is that this research develops a children's storybook oriented to Pancasila students' profiles. The main values of the Pancasila student profile are faith, fear of God, noble character, global diversity, cooperation, independence, critical reasoning, and creativity. This research aims to create a children's storybook oriented to the student profile of Pancasila chapter 6, *Indonesiaku Kaya Budaya*, fourth grade SD/MI for fourth-grade students.

2. METHOD

This type of research is development research because the focus of this research is the development of a Children's Storybook with a profile-oriented Pancasila student profile in the science lesson chapter 6 *Indonesiaku Kaya Budaya* for fourth-grade elementary school students. This study uses a 4-D research model developed by S. Thiagarajan, Dorothy S. Sammel, and Melvyn I. Sammel. The 4D model consists of four development stages: define, design, develop, and disseminate (Batubara, 2017). The subjects in this study were three experts to validate the feasibility of the material, the appropriateness of language, and the feasibility of the graphic of the storybook developed using the validation sheet. The fourth-grade teacher at SD Negeri 3 Tigawasa

will provide an assessment of the practicality of the book through a teacher response questionnaire. Fourth-grade students of SD Negeri 3 Tigawasa, Banjar District, totaling 34 students, assess the practicality of the storybooks developed. The data in this study were collected through library research, field studies, observations, questionnaires, and interviews. These data were collected using several instruments, namely validation sheets, and response questionnaires. The research questionnaire grid is presented in Table 1, Table 2, and Table 3.

Table 1. Validation Grid

No	Components	Indicators	Number
1.	Material Eligibility	Compatibility with chapters and subchapters	1, 2
		Conformity with learning outcomes and learning objectives	3, 4
		Oriented Pancasila student profile (devotion to God and having a noble character)	5, 6, 7
		Oriented Pancasila student profile (global diversity)	8, 9, 10
		Oriented Pancasila student profile (independent)	11, 12, 13
		Oriented Pancasila student profile (Gotong royong)	14, 15, 16
		Oriented Pancasila student profile (critical reasoning)	17, 18,
2.	Language Eligibility	Oriented to the main values of Pancasila's student profile (creative)	19
		straightforward	20
		Communicative	21
		Dialogic and Interactive	22, 23
		Suitability with student development	24, 25
3.	Feasibility of Graphics	Conformity with Indonesian language rules	26, 27
		Layout	28
		Image Quality	29, 30
		Color composition	31, 32
		Typography	33, 34, 35

Table 2. Teacher Response Questionnaire

No	Components	Indicators	Items
1	Interest	Book display	1
		Material presentation	2, 3,
		Illustration	4, 5
		Convenience	6
		Suitability	7, 8, 9, 10
2	Material	Oriented Student Profile Pancasila (fearfulness to God)	11, 12, 13
		Oriented Pancasila Student Profile (independent)	14, 15, 16
		Oriented Pancasila Student Profile (global diversity)	17, 18, 19
		Oriented Pancasila Student Profile (gotong royong)	20, 21, 22
		Oriented Pancasila Student Profile (critical reasoning)	23, 24, 25
3	Language	(Creative)	25
		Clarity	26, 27, 28
		Typography	29, 30

Table 3. Student Response Questionnaire

No	Components	Indicators	Items
1	Interest	Book display	1, 2, 3
2	Material	Illustration	4, 5
		Convenience	6, 7
3	Language	Suitability	8
		Clarity	9
		Typography	10

Obtaining the storybook effectiveness test results using a one-shot case study. This one-shot case study method is where one experimental group is given treatment. The level of effectiveness is obtained from the pre-test and post-test results on the literacy of students' Pancasila values.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

The procedure or development stages used in the research using the 4D model are divided into four stages: Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate. The design of this storybook begins with the process of preparing a storyboard (draft of story sketches) made on paper manually, which is then poured into a clean sketch using the Krita software. Compiling illustrations on the Krita software begins with the preparation of rough sketches, clean sketches, basic colors, texturing, and additional finishing by giving a collage effect so that the illustration looks as if it was made by sticking pieces of paper. The illustration is then added with text and editing layout using Photoshop Software. The next stage is the development stage. Three experts and one practitioner further validated the storybooks produced at this stage. The results of the validity test of the developed storybook were declared "very valid" with an average score of "4.9". Experts and practitioners have completed several notes and suggestions on the validation sheet. The first expert advises paying attention to the color in story books. The second expert gives notes to pay attention to the size of the writing and the color of the image to make it look brighter. Practitioners gave suggestions to adjust the colors in the pictures.

At this stage, the storybooks are validated by experts and practitioners and revised according to the notes, and suggestions are then distributed to be tested for use in learning. The storybooks were distributed to 34 students in the fourth grade of SD Negeri 3 Tigawasa. Teacher and student responses were taken through a questionnaire. The teacher's response questionnaire consists of several positive statements, with five alternative answers: strongly agree, agree, quite agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. In contrast, the student response questionnaire consists of several questions that students answer with Yes or No. Experiments in learning are carried out directly to 4th-grade students of SD Negeri 3 Tigawasa. Furthermore, the teacher said that learning on that day would use learning media in the form of storybooks that had been distributed. At the end of the lesson, students will be asked to respond to learning activities using storybooks distributed by the teacher. The teacher assisted in filling out the questionnaire for students, making it easier for them to fill it out. The teacher also filled out a response questionnaire based on his experience using story books in teaching activities. Based on the results of these trials, the teacher response questionnaire analysis is presented in [Table 4](#).

Table 4. The Results of the Teacher's Response Questionnaire Analysis

No	Aspect	Score
1.	Interest	24
2.	Theory	95,5
3.	Language	25
Total		144,5
Score		4.82
Category		Very Practical

Based on the practicality test criteria calculation, the teacher's response scored 4.82 in a very practical category. Then based on the practicality test calculation of student responses to story books, the results were 98.5. These results indicate that the storybook meets the very practical criteria. After that, the effectiveness test was carried out by calculating the N-Gain. Based on the calculation of the average gain score, the average result is 0.71, meaning that the storybook developed has a high level of effectiveness. The result of the development of this research is a children's storybook oriented to the profile of Pancasila students for chapter 6, Indonesiaku Kaya Budaya Fourth grade SD/MI, which was developed based on the 4D development model.

Discussion

This research is a research and development (Research and Development) which aims to produce a product in the form of a children's storybook with a profile oriented to Pancasila students in the culturally rich Indonesian chapter for fourth-grade elementary school students. The children's storybook oriented to the Pancasila student profile for chapter 6 Indonesiaku Kaya Budaya fourth grade of SD/MI is suitable for the learning process. It can be seen from several aspects. First, the aspect of the material presented in the picture book follows the basic competencies and learning objectives. In addition, picture storybook media is suitable for learning because of the attractive packaging of the material. The choice of media must be adjusted to the subject matter because each lesson's content has different characteristics (Siwi Pawestri Apriliani & Radia, 2020; Leksana, 2019). Appropriate media and material content will result in interactive learning so that learning materials can be delivered properly. Appropriate media and material content will result in interactive learning so that learning materials can be delivered properly (Siwi Pawestri Apriliani & Radia, 2020; Faroh & Setiawan, 2018). The content of the subject matter will be conveyed properly if it is accompanied by the use of media that is appropriate to the situation and conditions (I. M. A Dharma, 2019; Sapri et al., 2022). Picture story book media is a learning media designed based on several collections of images and text. The use of storybook media can attract students' attention, and the material taught will be remembered longer because, in the picture book itself,

the material is packaged through interesting pictures (Hayati & Suparno, 2020; Sumiati & Tirtayani, 2021). Thus, a children's storybook with a profile oriented to Pancasila students in the culturally rich Indonesia chapter for fourth-grade elementary school students is appropriate to use.

Second, this storybook will later be able to assist teachers in exemplifying and cultivating the values of Pancasila student profiles because, in addition to educating with illustrations in books, students will be interested in reading them. Literature is the right medium for character-building and social-spiritual attitudes (Samsiyah, 2019; Wahyuni, 2017). Furthermore, Warsa said that literature is a method of character cultivation called the "value clarification" method. By consuming stories with religious or social nuances, they will be able to provide meaningful learning to the nation's children, especially in forming attitudes (Aryanto & Widiensyah, 2019; Juanda, 2019; Ridwan, 2016). Children's story books are a media from print technology used to convey material (Halim & Munthe, 2019b; Prayoga et al., 2017). Media illustrated children's stories are children's stories that are given additional illustrations that reflect the story's contents. Story books, especially picture story books, are easy-to-use media because they do not require other additional tools or special facilities, so it can be said that their use is very practical (Siwi Pawestri Apriliani & Radia, 2020; Munandar et al., 2018; Ratnasari, 2019). Children's stories are not only practical and entertaining but can also contain educational values in them. Children's educational stories, better known as didactic literature, are literary works with elements implied in the storyline so that readers gain knowledge after reading them. Literature in elementary schools should be adapted to the curriculum as contained in the curriculum. Learning literature requires students to enjoy and utilize literary works to develop personality, broaden life horizons, and improve knowledge and language skills.

This finding is reinforced by previous research stating that this picture storybook media is suitable for use during the learning process in class because it has obtained a good or very good category (Siwi Pawestri Apriliani & Radia, 2020; I Made Aditya Dharma, 2019). Picture storybook media can attract students' attention and can motivate students to be active in learning (Paramita et al., 2022; Sumiati & Tirtayani, 2021). The existence of children's storybook media with a profile oriented to Pancasila students in the theme of Indonesiaku rich in culture for fourth-grade elementary school students can help students in the learning process. But it cannot be separated from the teacher's supervision to help students in the learning process. Thus, students can become more active and interested, positively affecting learning outcomes. This research implies that it is hoped that the existence of children's storybook media with the orientation of Pancasila student profiles in the theme of Indonesiaku rich in culture for fourth-grade elementary school students as a learning support tool can attract students' attention, motivate students to be more active and make learning more varied. The selection of learning materials that can be oriented to the profile of Pancasila students must be made properly so that they can be conveyed properly to students.

4. CONCLUSION

Children's storybooks with a profile oriented to Pancasila students in the theme of Indonesia, I'm Rich in Culture, for fourth-grade elementary school students have a high level of effectiveness and can be used in the learning process so that this storybook can be used as teaching material to exemplify and cultivate the values of the Pancasila student profile.

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